

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' IDEAS ABOUT UZBEK MUSIC FOLKLORE.

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Abstract: In educational institutions, listening to happy and exciting songs, clapping and accompanying children's musical instruments during music classes will increase their passion for music. Because children of this age do not yet have full attention, they tend to be more active and play. The development of musical abilities in the student during music lessons should always be the focus of the educator, music director, and should be carried out with the help of various methods and tools, including musical-didactic games.

Main part: Children's music folklore, which is one of the main links of Uzbek music folklore, occupies a special place in Uzbek music culture. Because it reflects children's unique world, children's outlook, interests and aspirations, dreams and hopes. One of the most important aspects of musical folklore is its nationalism. The works of this genre are simple, quickly reach the listener and the performer, musical themes and motifs are easy to understand. In addition, folklore music is distinguished by its uniqueness, universality, reflection of people's dreams, aspirations, joys and worries, and daily lifestyle. These characteristics distinguish folk music from all other musical genres.

The socio-psychological features of forming ideas about Uzbek music folklore are of special importance in the formation of students' skills and interests in music and culture. These properties are defined as follows:

The problem of identity and nationality: Uzbek musical folklore is important in students' understanding and appreciation of their national identity. These imaginations help students to see themselves in their historical and cultural contexts.

✚ **Social integration:** formation of ideas about Uzbek musical folklore helps students' social integration, strengthens and unites their inter-ethnic relations.

✚ **Helping and supporting:** Forming ideas about Uzbek music folklore helps students to support themselves and communicate with other cultures.

✚ **Creative activity:** forming ideas about Uzbek musical folklore develops creative activity in students and strengthens their creative abilities.

✚ **Educational impact:** Forming ideas about Uzbek musical folklore has an educational impact on students and focuses them on justice, fairness and respect.

For these reasons, the socio-psychological features of forming students' imaginations about Uzbek musical folklore are very important and are of great importance in developing their cultural interests and skills.

✚ Folklore is a style of music that expresses the historical, cultural and social values of a nation. The local music style is a music style that is unique to a nation and represents the main parts of its cultural and spiritual life.

✚ The difference between folklore and local music style is related to their origin and historical development. Folk music is usually formed on the basis of historical and national values and represents the musical traditions of various Uzbek nations. The local music style

expresses the unique musical characteristics of the defined geographical area and illuminates its spiritual and cultural experience.

✚ Folklore and local music style will be important for students to understand and appreciate their national identity. They help students to present themselves in their historical and cultural context and allow them to social integration and integration.

✚ Folklore and local music styles also help to develop creative activity in students and strengthen their creative abilities. Also, these methods have an educational effect on students and focus them on justice, fairness and respect.

Along with these, folklore and local music styles are very important in forming perceptions of Uzbek musical folklore and play a major role in developing students' cultural interests and skills.

Summary: There are different types of "Yor-yor" that are sung in wedding ceremonies. They were performed solo and as a team by the women's choir. In fact, these are all types of folk choirs. Their styles of performance are extremely rich, and they are sung by hitting circles, karagyot, clapping, rustling, angishvona and cymbals.

Do not take any of the current professional songs (be it "Shodlik" or "Dutorchi girls"), elements of two voices are naturally heard in their performance. If during the time of the Soviets, the performance of the artists in foreign countries was organized mainly on the basis of European art, then in the conditions of the independence of our country, the fact that the artists of Uzbekistan began to go abroad based on the culture of their national singing will increase its social and cultural prestige. . Today, representatives of the art field should focus on issues of the Motherland, patriotism, duty, national idea, national ideology, and national pride. The task before our composers is to create even more songs that all the people of Uzbekistan can join and sing together and whose content is mixed with the feeling of the Motherland.

References:

1. Umurova, M. Y., & Nurullaeva, N. K. (2020). ТЕОРИЯ И МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ (ПО ОБЛАСТЯМ И УРОВНЯМ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ). Проблемы педагогики, 40.
2. Yorievna, U. M. R., & Karimovna, N. N. (2020). Innovative approach to the development of musical abilities in children with disabilities health opportunities. Проблемы педагогики, (2 (47)).
3. Yoshiyevna, U. M. R., & O'G'Li, R. A. R. (2021). MUSIQA MADANIYATI DARSLARIDA "VENA KLASSIK MAKTABI" NAMOYONDALARI HAYOTI VA IJODIYIY FAOLIYATI BILAN TANISHTIRISH USLUBLARI. Scientific progress, 1(3).
4. Алаева, З. М. (2020). Педагогика как наука и искусство воспитания. Вестник науки и образования, (21-2 (99)).
5. Rajabov, A. (2020). The development of music and instrumental performance in Central Asia. International Journal of Applied Research, 6(5).
6. Radjabov, A., & Kenjabonu, T. (2021). CONTENT OF PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR DEVELOPMENT IN ACCOUNT PROCESS. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 1(01), 54-61.]
7. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-zbek-musiqa-folklori-namunalarini-to-plash-va-yozib-olish-tarixidan>
8. <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/issue/view/113>
9. <file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/o-zbek-musiqa-folklori-namunalarini-to-plash-va-yozib-olish-tarixidan.pdf>
10. https://uniwork.buxdu.uz/resurs/13039_1_FFC00E759FBCD2B86575F05B6D3F0C47D3F36794.pdf